

United States Department of the Interior

FISH AND WILDLIFE SERVICE
San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish & Wildlife Office
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Sacramento, California 95814-4700

In reply refer to:

2023-0013317-S7-001-R001

September 30, 2024

Sarra C. Kubinec
Project Manager, Regulatory Division
U.S. Army Corps of Engineers
San Francisco District
450 Golden Gate Avenue
San Francisco, California 94102-3406

Subject: Reinitiation of Informal and Formal Consultation Appending the Amorco Marine Terminal Repairs Project (U.S. Army Corps of Engineers File Number: SPN-2005-294800) to the December 1, 2004, Formal Programmatic Consultation on the Issuance of Section 10 and 404 Permits for Projects with Relatively Small Effects on the Delta Smelt (*Hypomesus transpacificus*) and its Critical Habitat (U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service File Number: 1-1-04-F-0345)

Dear Ms. Kubinec:

This letter is in response to the U.S. Army Corps of Engineers' (Corps) August 27, 2024, letter requesting reinitiation of the February 17, 2023 formal and informal consultation with the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (Service) on the proposed Amorco Marine Terminal Repairs Project (proposed project) in Martinez, Contra Costa County, California to reflect changes in the *Description of the Proposed Action* and inclusion of the federally endangered San Francisco Bay-Delta distinct population segment (DPS) of the longfin smelt (longfin smelt DPS; *Spirinchus thaleichthys*). The Corps determined the proposed project with changes may affect, but is not likely to adversely affect the federally endangered salt marsh harvest mouse (*Reithrodontomys raviventris*), endangered Ridgway's rail (*Rallus obsoletus obsoletus*), threatened delta smelt (*Hypomesus transpacificus*), and its critical habitat and the endangered longfin smelt DPS.

As noted in email correspondence for this reinitiation and the 2023 consultation and consistent with the February 17, 2023 consultation appending the proposed project to the Service's December 1, 2004, *Formal Programmatic Consultation on the Issuance of Section 10 and 404 Permits for Projects with Relatively Small Effects on the Delta Smelt (Hypomesus transpacificus) and its Critical Habitat* (Programmatic Biological Opinion) the Service does not concur with the

Corps' not likely to adversely affect determinations for the delta smelt, its critical habitat, or the longfin smelt DPS. This response is provided under the authority of the Endangered Species Act of 1973, as amended (16 U.S.C. 1531 *et seq.*) (Act), and in accordance with the implementing regulations pertaining to interagency cooperation (50 CFR § 402).

In reviewing this reinitiation request, the Service has relied upon: (1) the August 27, 2024, letter requesting reinitiation consultation and the associated enclosures (including the April 10, 2024 memorandum from ERM, Inc.); (2) the Service's February 17, 2023, formal and informal consultation (Service File Number: 2023-0013317-S7-001); (3) several emails between the Corps and Service; (4) the August 28, 2024, email from the proposed project proponent's consultant (ERM Inc.) with a tracked-changes version of the 2023 consultation reflecting the 2024 proposed project changes; and (5) other information available to the Service.

The Service concurs with the Corps' determination that the proposed project changes may affect but is not likely to adversely affect the salt marsh harvest mouse and California Ridgway's rail. Although tidal marsh habitat is present where the Amorco Marine Terminal connects landside, it is a small narrow strip of brackish marsh habitat that abuts ruderal and coastal scrub habitat. Higher quality habitat is located west of the Amorco Marine Terminal outside of the Action Area. No work will be done within vegetated marsh habitats and noise from temporary impacts or vibratory pile driving is not expected to extend into suitable habitat per the analysis in the April 10, 2024, ERM Inc. memorandum.

The remainder of the document is the reinitiated formal consultation for the delta smelt, its critical habitat, and the longfin smelt DPS. Because this is a multi-year project the Service is reissuing the full document with changed text noted by underline for additions and strike out for deletions as appropriate.

Consultation History

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|--------------------------|--|
| January 11, 2023 | The Service received the Corps' request for informal consultation. |
| January 11-12, 2023 | The Service and Corps exchanged emails regarding the Programmatic Biological Opinion and previous consultation. |
| January 26, 2023 | The Service received the Corps' revised consultation request email to append the project to the Programmatic Biological Opinion. |
| February 6-7, 2023 | The Service and Corps exchanged emails regarding the option to conference on the proposed listed as endangered longfin smelt (<i>Spirinchus thaleichthys</i>) and a revision to the Conservation Measures. The Corps declined to conference on the longfin smelt citing internal guidance to defer until the listing decision is made. |
| <u>February 17, 2023</u> | <u>The Service issued the informal consultation concurring with the Corps'</u> |

determination on the California Ridgway's [clapper] rail and salt marsh harvest mouse and the formal consultation appending the proposed project to the Programmatic Biological Opinion.

July 16, 2024 The Service received the Corps' request for a new informal consultation.

July-August 2024 The Service and Corps exchanged emails regarding reinitiation of the existing consultation, species determinations, and the Service's request for a tracked changes version of the 2023 consultation with project and effects changes incorporated.

August 27, 2024 The Service received the Corps' revised request from a new consultation to a reinitiation but the species determinations were unchanged.

August 28, 2024 The Service received a tracked changes version of the 2023 consultation from ERM Inc.

Description of the Proposed Action (underline for additions/strike out for deletions)

The proposed project would repair damaged piles, replace piles with damage too extensive to repair, ~~and~~ repair pile caps and/or joists along the length of the marine terminal, and implement structural modifications. Construction activities will occur along the length of the Amorco Marine Terminal, from ~~approximately 30 feet from~~ the shoreline to the berth, located approximately 1,500 feet into the Carquinez Strait. Work to be performed for the proposed project includes repair of the piles associated with Dolphins A-32, A-33, A-36, ~~and~~ A-68, A-77, and A-79, and Trestles B ~~and~~ D, E, and the Main Pipeway Trestle. Repairs will also include pile cap and/or joist or brace repairs at Dolphins A-32, A-36, A-35, A-34, A-33, A-69, A-70, A-74, Trestles A, B, C, D, A-80, and A-69, and the Main Pipeway Trestle, and repairs to concrete beams/slabs at A-79, A-78, A-80, A-77, and Trestles E and A. The wood deck at Dolphins A-79, A-36, A-34, and Trestles D and B will be replaced. Handrails will be repaired at Dolphin A-74, and Trestles B, and A-69. Structural modifications will consist of the removal of Dolphins A-73 and A-72 and the adjoining A-72 Platform, which will be replaced by the installation of intermediary platforms, catwalks, and walkways; the fire monitor that is encompassed by Dolphin A-73 but sits on its own piling will be maintained and a new steel platform supported by four (4) new steel piles will be installed around the existing fire monitor/pile where Dolphin A-73 is removed.

Depending on the level of damage, some piles may need to be fully replaced instead of repaired. In addition, during implementation of the repairs, the need for additional pile repairs and replacements may be identified. Additional repairs not identified in this consultation may require reinitiation of this consultation.

Pile Repairs

For offshore pile repairs, a spud barge will be used for deeper-water work, while repairs in water

too shallow for the barge will require work from the Main Pipeway Trestle, in-water personnel, and/or a shallow-drafted vessel. To prevent movement of the barge during construction, vertical steel shafts (spuds) will be inserted into the sediment at the fore and aft ends of the barge. A diesel engine-powered spud winch will be used to raise and lower the spuds when the barge needs to be moved. The spud entry locations into the sediment are the only expected sediment interaction locations for the proposed project.

For pile repairs within the shoreline, a boat will be used to approach the pile from the water. The vessel will be beached at the immediate repair area, characterized by unvegetated shoreline, for up to two (2) days. No vegetation removal or ground disturbance is anticipated.

Repair of the piles will consist of placing a fiberglass (e.g., “Fox” or equivalent) sleeve around the portion of the pile to be repaired and pumping grout into the sleeve via a hose that is connected to a pump situated on the wharf. The grout will be mixed using a portable mixer on the wharf. The proposed pile repairs will require work above and below the waterline, with repairs on each pile requiring the sleeve to be placed on, but not in, the substrate. The spud entry locations into the sediment, the sleeve placement on the substrate, and the potential personnel entry in shallow water are the only expected sediment interactions from repair activities.

Pile Replacement and Installation

For piles that require replacement, the pile cap will be removed from the Terminal deck, then a spud barge will be maneuvered into place and a barge crane will grab the pile, vibrate it out of the substrate, and place a new pile into the same hole. A diesel hammer will then be used to pile-drive the replacement pile into position. Finally, personnel will repair the Terminal deck. Pile replacement work will occur both above and below the Mean Higher High Water (MHHW) mark. Sediment interactions from replacement activities will occur from the pile removal and replacement and the spud entry locations.

Installation of the new steel piles will be performed by a crane barge. The crane will set the pile into the mudline and then a vibratory hammer will drive the pile to the specified depth. If it is found that vibratory installation is inadequate or if the pile(s) encounter obstructions below the mudline, a diesel hammer pile driver may be used. Sediment interactions from pile installation activities will occur from pile installation and spud entry locations.

Pile Cap, Brace, and Joist Repairs

Pile cap, brace, and joist repairs will be performed from the Amorco Marine Terminal deck or by using scaffolding suspended below the deck. No work will occur in the water and a tarp will be suspended from the scaffolding to prevent material from entering the water.

Dolphin Removal

During demolition activities, materials will be removed from the dolphins and placed onto a waste barge or a marine spud barge using a crane on the spud barge, including the removal of the

piles. Piles will be removed by removing the wharf timber surface, then the pile caps, and then vibrating and pulling the piles out of the substrate using a barge crane. Holes in substrate where piles are removed will be left to fill in naturally. If a damaged pile breaks or will not come loose from the substrate, the pile will be cut off at three feet below the mudline. After the removal of Dolphins A-73 and A-72, a crane barge will be used to install the new catwalks and support platforms between the remaining structures. Sediment interactions from dolphin removal and catwalk and support platform installation will occur from the pile removal and the spud entry locations.

Schedule and Access

The work ~~is scheduled to~~ commenced in 2023 with new scope changes scheduled to commence in 2024 and will be conducted over a 5-year period, with in-water work scheduled to occur between August 1 and November 30. Construction will take place during daylight hours only.

Materials will be brought in by marine barge for the parts of the repair work located in deep enough water for barge access. In locations along the Main Pipeway Trestle where water is too shallow for a barge, the material will be brought in by truck along Amorco Road; access to the pile repair on the shoreline will be by boat. No access will occur along the shoreline.

Conservation Measures

The Service included general and specific measures from the biological assessment that pertain to the Service's jurisdictional species and omitted measures that do not pertain to our species under this consultation.

1. Pile driving will always use a soft start procedure. The soft start would include an initial set of three strikes from the impact hammer at reduced energy, followed by a 1-minute waiting period. This process will be repeated a total of three times prior to initiation of pile driving. Soft start is required for any impact driving, including at the beginning of the day and at any time following a cessation of impact pile driving of 30 minutes or longer.
2. Ensure that each construction crew (including cleanup crews) has sufficient supplies of absorbent and barrier materials onsite at all times to allow the rapid containment and recovery of spilled materials, and that each construction crew knows the procedure for reporting spills.
3. Ensure that each construction crew has sufficient tools and material onsite at all times to stop leaks.
4. Know the contact names and telephone numbers for all Marathon refinery contacts and local, State, and Federal agencies (including, if necessary, the U.S. Coast Guard and the National Response Center) that might need to be notified in the event of a spill.

5. Follow the requirements of those agencies in cleaning up the spill, excavating and disposing of soils or other materials contaminated by a spill, and collecting and disposing of waste generated during spill cleanup.
6. No equipment or vehicles shall be stored, maintained or washed in any area on the Amorco Marine Terminal to reduce the potential for any spills or debris entering the water column.
7. All fuel, waste, oils, and solvents shall be stored away from the construction site. Any spills shall be contained and properly disposed of.
8. All vehicles and equipment shall be properly maintained to reduce the potential for spills of petroleum-based products.
9. If any materials or wastes are released to the Bay, project supervisors shall immediately halt all work and use all available resources to assure containment and removal.
10. Best Management Practices shall be consistently employed to help prevent pollutants from entering Bay waters.
11. Employees, subcontractors, and vendors will be informed, educated, and trained to understand the applicable practices and procedures for the various construction activities being done.
12. The construction site shall be maintained by the contractor in such a condition that any storms do not carry wastes or pollutants offsite. Upon completion of the proposed project, all equipment will be safely demobilized from the area.
13. At the end of each day of construction activity, all construction debris and waste materials shall be collected and properly disposed of by the contractor in the appropriate trash or recycling bins.
14. All construction personnel will receive environmental awareness training before commencing work on the proposed project. The training will be prepared by a biologist familiar with the species of concern that may be present at or near the proposed project, and will cover listed species that may be present, environmental laws and protections, and permit conditions.
15. No equipment staging, access, or work activities shall be conducted within natural terrestrial habitat along the shoreline.
16. In-water work will be limited to August 1 through November 30.

17. To avoid degradation of marsh habitats work will be restricted to the non-vegetated shoreline. No staging or beaching will occur within native vegetation. No vegetation will be removed.
18. Prepare and implement an environmental resources worker training covering sensitive resources, including California Ridgway's rail and salt marsh harvest mouse, which may be encountered during work.
19. Onshore pile repair activities shall be conducted under the supervision of a qualified biologist. This monitor will conduct an initial site inspection and watch for listed wildlife species and temporarily stop work if listed species are encountered. Wildlife will be allowed to leave the proposed project site on their own before work is allowed to resume. The biologist will document compliance with permit conditions. Please note, if California Ridgway's rails or salt marsh harvest mice are encountered, reinitiation of consultation may be required.
20. Onshore pile repair work will not occur within 2 hours before or after extreme high tides (6.5 feet or above, as measured at the Golden Gate Bridge), when the marsh plain is inundated.

Action Area

The Action Area is defined in 50 CFR § 402.02, as "all areas to be affected directly or indirectly by the Federal action and not merely the immediate area involved in the action." The Action Area for this consultation encompasses all areas that may be directly or indirectly affected as a result of activities for the project and the broader area that, while outside the project footprint, may be directly or indirectly affected by vibrations, noise, lighting, or movement associated with the proposed project. Based on the noise analysis presented in the biological assessment the Action Area includes the length of the wharf where work would occur as well as a 710-foot radius around all replacement piles, a 100-foot radius around all repaired piles, and a 330-foot radius around all above-water work for an estimated area of 50 acres. Based on a revised noise analysis presented in the ERM, Inc. April 10, 2024 memorandum, the Action Area includes a 5.3-mile radius around the four steel piles during impact driving (limited to the shoreline edge of the Carquinez Strait) for aquatic impacts and a 39-foot radius around steel piles for noise impacts above water for an estimated total area of 10,000 acres (refer to the April 10, 2024 memorandum for two untitled figures depicting the Action Area).

Status of Species

Delta Smelt

The status of the species has been updated since the issuance of the Programmatic Biological Opinion. Please refer to the 2022 delta smelt Species Assessment and Listing Priority Assignment Form of the Candidate Notice of Review for the status of the species. Electronic copies of this

document are available at https://ecosphere-documents-production-public.s3.amazonaws.com/sams/public_docs/publication/4119.pdf (Service 2023).

In December 2021, the Service, along with the California Department of Fish and Wildlife, California Department of Water Resources, and U.S. Bureau of Reclamation, began releasing captively produced delta smelt into the Sacramento-San Joaquin River Delta in an experiment intended to help inform future supplementation of the species in the wild. Experimental release of captively produced, marked delta smelt continued for a third year from November 2023 through January 2024. During this third year a total of 91,468 delta smelt were released over 6 release periods in the Sacramento River at Rio Vista. A small subsample of those marked fish have also been recaptured. A fourth year of experimental release is planned for the winter 2024-2025.

The status of the species has been updated since the issuance of the Programmatic Biological Opinion. Please refer to the 2021 delta smelt 5-year review Species Assessment and Listing Priority Assignment Form and page 26172 of the 2021 Candidate Notice of Review for the status of the species. Electronic copies of these documents are available at <https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/tess/publication/3707.pdf> and <https://www.govinfo.gov/content/pkg/FR-2022-05-03/pdf/2022-09376.pdf#page=1>.

The 2021 California Department of Fish and Wildlife (CDFW) Fall Midwater Trawl (FMWT) Index was 0 for the fourth year in a row. The CDFW Spring Kodiak Trawl (SKT) monitors the adult spawning stock of delta smelt and serves as an indication for the relative number and distribution of spawners in the system. The 2021 SKT Relative Abundance Index was 0, the lowest on record.

The CDFW methods generate abundance indices from each survey but each index is on a different numeric scale. This means the index number generated by a given survey only has quantitative meaning relative to other indices generated by the same survey. Further, the CDFW indices lack estimates of uncertainty (variability) which limits interpretation of abundance changes from year to year even within each sampling program. In 2019, the Service completed a new delta smelt abundance indexing procedure using data from all four CDFW surveys (FMWT, summer townet, 20-mm, and SKT) (Polansky *et al.* 2019). The Service method improves upon the CDFW method because it generates abundance indices in units of numbers of fish, including attempts to correct for different sampling efficiencies among surveys, and the method includes measures of uncertainty. Service indices of spawner abundance based on combined January and February SKT sampling are listed with their confidence intervals in Table 1. The estimates show the most recent 20 years of the delta smelt's longer-term decline in numbers of fish as best as they can be approximated with currently available information.

The Service's Enhanced Delta Smelt Monitoring (EDSM) is designed to complete Delta wide surveys at a weekly time scale while SKT does this at a monthly scale, so the Service calculated EDSM abundance estimates using all weekly survey data within the January-February time interval (Table 2). For both surveys, data collected from January and February of each year were combined to derive a single abundance estimate. Beginning in 2022, estimates include cultured delta smelt released in the Delta between December 2021 and February 2022 described below

and in Table 3. The effects of survey specific sampling times and locations in relation to release times and locations have not been fully evaluated.

In December 2021, the Service, along with CDFW, California Department of Water Resources (DWR), and U.S. Bureau of Reclamation (Reclamation), began experimentally releasing captively produced delta smelt into the Sacramento-San Joaquin River Delta in an experiment intended to help inform future supplementation of the species in the wild. A total of 5 releases totaling 55,733 brood year 2021 marked (adipose fin clip or Visible Implant Elastomer (VIE) delta smelt from UC Davis' Fish Conservation and Culture Laboratory. The releases occurred in various locations including Rio Vista, the Sacramento Deep Water Ship Channel, and Suisun Marsh. A subsample of those marked fish were recaptured in the Deep Water Ship Channel, central Delta, south Delta, and Suisun March by EDSM, Chipps Island Trawl, SKT, Bay Study, and in the Central Valley Project (CVP) salvage facility.

Experimental release of captively produced, marked delta smelt continued for a second year in November 2022 through January 2023. These releases occurred at both Rio Vista and the Sacramento Deep Water Ship Channel. A total of 43,705 delta smelt were released (Table 4). A small subsample of those marked fish have also been recaptured.

Table 1. Spring Kodiak Trawl (SKT) Survey abundance estimates and related statistics and data summaries. The Year-to-Year Ratio column shows the population growth rate from one year to the next, calculated as the ratio of abundances from consecutive years. *Data from only February was used because SKT sampling did not take place in January.

Year	Abundance Estimate	Standard Error	95% Confidence Interval		Total delta smelt caught (total tows) by the SKT survey		Year-to-Year Ratio
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound	January	February	
2002	1,093,244	195,329	760,332	1,523,294	262 (35)	394(39)	NA
2003*	996,055	261,205	581,197	1,597,198	NA (0)	232 (39)	0.91
2004	966,981	262,190	553,729	1,573,002	380 (39)	300(34)	0.97
2005	715,858	147,190	470,572	1,044,828	220 (39)	218 (40)	0.74
2006	272,327	42,400	198,681	364,438	44 (40)	84 (40)	0.38
2007	449,466	128,731	249,216	749,168	109 (40)	107 (39)	1.65
2008	509,428	188,396	236,859	963,839	132 (40)	36 (39)	1.13
2009	1,166,145	523,856	459,083	2,464,804	579 (40)	61 (42)	2.29
2010	251,863	54,580	161,753	374,582	88 (41)	57 (41)	0.22

2011	461,599	202,547	185,712	962,088		177 (42)	128 (40)	1.83
2012	1,177,201	328,682	662,728	1,939,836		320 (42)	287 (42)	2.55
2013	333,682	89,809	191,886	541,064		100 (41)	125 (41)	0.28
2014	308,972	91,474	167,858	522,884		148 (40)	55 (40)	0.93
2015	213,345	76,639	101,434	397,439		21 (39)	68 (39)	0.69
2016	25,445	9,584	11,661	48,622		7 (40)	6 (39)	0.12
2017	73,331	23,342	38,010	128,459		18 (38)	8 (41)	2.88
2018	26,649	21,397	5,215	82,805		10 (40)	4 (41)	0.36
2019	5,610	4,395	1,138	17,135		1 (40)	1 (39)	0.21
2020	5,213	3,644	1,241	14,710		1 (39)	1 (40)	0.93
2021	0	Not Defined	Not Defined	Not Defined		0 (39)	0 (36)	0
2022	12,679	9,033	2,942	36,250		0 (36)	5 (40)	NA

Table 2. Enhanced Delta Smelt Monitoring (EDSM) Survey abundance estimates with columns as in Table 2

Year	Abundance Estimate	Standard Error	95% Confidence Interval		Total delta smelt caught (total tows) by the EDSM survey		Year-to-Year Ratio
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound	January	February	
2017	85,162	21,362	50,902	134,047	54 (401)	33 (684)	NA
2018	6,821	2,778	2,931	13,614	10 (727)	3 (610)	0.08
2019	4,500	1,075	2,758	6,947	17 (724)	7 (518)	0.66
2020	1,079	544	379	2,448	3 (625)	2 (606)	0.23
2021	267	189	63	760	2 (327)	0 (466)	0.26
2022	4,909	2,232	1,911	10,450	6 (468)	12 (484)	18.39

Table 3: Summary of delta smelt releases for December 2021 through February 2022.

Release	Site	Date(s)	Total Released
1	Rio Vista	Dec 14-15, 2021	12,800
2	Rio Vista	Jan 11-12, 2022	12,800

3	Sacramento Deep Water Ship Channel	Feb 3, 2022	6,400
4	Suisun Marsh	Feb 9-10, 2022	12,800
5	Sacramento Deep Water Ship Channel	Feb 16-17, 2022	10,933

Table 4: Summary of delta smelt releases for November 2022 through January 2023.

Release Event	Release Date	Release Site	Release method	VIE (Side/color/Location)	Ad clip	Total released	Release status
1a	11/29/2022	Rio Vista	soft	Right/ blue/ PD	None	6,584	Complete
1b	11/30/2022	Rio Vista	hard	Left/ red/ AD	None	6,556	Complete
2a	01/18/2023 01/19/2023	Rio Vista	hard	Right/ orange/ PD	None	14,524	Complete
2b	01/18/2023	Rio Vista	Trailer release	None	Yes	3,046	Complete
3a	01/25/2023	SDWSC	hard	Left/ orange/ AD	None	6,775	Complete
3b	01/26/2023	SDWSC	soft	Right/ green/ PD	None	6,240	Complete
Total	-	-	-	-	-	43,705	-

Longfin Smelt DPS

The Service listed the longfin smelt DPS as endangered on July 30, 2024 (Service 2024a). For the comprehensive assessment of the longfin smelt DPS, please refer to the proposed listing rule at <https://www.govinfo.gov/content/pkg/FR-2024-07-30/pdf/2024-16380.pdf#page=1> and the *Species Status Assessment for the San Francisco Bay-Delta Distinct Population Segment of the Longfin Smelt* at <https://ecos.fws.gov/ServCat/DownloadFile/253023> (Service 2024b). Critical habitat has not yet been proposed.

Status of Critical Habitat

The Service designated critical habitat for the delta smelt on December 19, 1994 (Service 1994). The geographic area encompassed by the designation includes all water and all submerged lands below ordinary high water and the entire water column bounded by and contained in Suisun Bay (including the contiguous Grizzly and Honker Bays); the length of Goodyear, Suisun, Cutoff, First Mallard (Spring Branch), and Montezuma sloughs; and the existing contiguous waters

contained within the legal Delta (as defined in section 12220 of the California Water Code) (Service 1994).

The Service's primary objective in designating critical habitat was to identify the key components of delta smelt habitat that support successful completion of the life cycle, including spawning, larval and juvenile transport, rearing, and adult migration back to spawning sites. Delta smelt are endemic to the Bay-Delta and the vast majority only live one year. Thus, regardless of annual hydrology, the Bay-Delta estuary must provide suitable habitat all year, every year. The primary constituent elements (PCEs) essential to the conservation of the delta smelt are physical habitat, water, river flow, and salinity concentrations required to maintain delta smelt habitat for spawning, larval and juvenile transport, rearing, and adult migration (Service 1994).

Environmental Baseline

Environmental Baseline refers to the condition of the listed species or its designated critical habitat in the Action Area, without the consequences to the listed species or designated critical habitat caused by the proposed action. The *Environmental Baseline* includes the past and present impacts of all Federal, State, or private actions and other human activities in the Action Area, the anticipated impacts of all proposed Federal Projects in the Action Area that have already undergone formal or early section 7 consultation, and the impact of State or private actions which are contemporaneous with the consultation in process. The consequences to listed species or designated critical habitat from ongoing agency activities or existing agency facilities that are not within the agency's discretion to modify are part of the *Environmental Baseline*.

The Amorco Marine Terminal is located in the open water and nearshore shallow waters of the Carquinez Strait. The Amorco Marine Terminal is a 1,130-foot-long wharf arm connected to the shore by approximately 1,500 feet of approach trestle (Main Pipeway Trestle) and is composed of wood, concrete, and metal. The wharf has four small buildings onsite, including two buildings for personnel, a pump house, and a tool shed. Existing lights are situated regularly along the wharf arm and approach trestle, and there is one large light bank under the main loading arm.

The Terminal extends from the shoreline of the city of Martinez into the Carquinez Strait and is approximately 500 feet west of the Benicia-Martinez Bridge. The Carquinez Strait is a narrow gap in the Coast Range that connects San Pablo Bay with Suisun Bay and the Sacramento-San Joaquin River Delta.

Delta Smelt and its Critical Habitat

Delta smelt are known to occur in Carquinez Strait and may occur in the open waters within and adjacent to the Action Area throughout the year if habitat conditions warrant. The aquatic portions of the Action Area are within designated critical habitat. Delta smelt may occur in the Action Area during the August 1-November 30 work window if the low salinity zone remains in Suisun Bay just east of the Carquinez Strait. Delta smelt are less likely to be in the Action Area if the low salinity zone is further upstream. As discussed in the *Status of the Species* section, delta smelt abundance is historically low and continues to trend downward with the exception of the

~~2021-2022~~ brood stock experimentally released fish.

~~California has been was in a multi-year year of drought. Over several months in 2021, Reclamation and DWR operated the CVP and SWP under a Temporary Urgency Change Petition (TUCP) to allow relaxation of D-1641 water quality standards. A rock barrier was installed at West False River in June 2021 and was in place until November 2022. In April 2022, Reclamation and DWR began operating under a TUCP for spring 2022 CVP and State Water Program operations. These factors contribute to the decline of the wild population and may negatively affect the experimentally released fish and their progeny. The January 2023 storms resulted in high turbid outflow and increased water supply but most of the state remains in drought status.~~

Longfin Smelt

Longfin smelt are known to occur in the Carquinez Strait and may occur in the open waters within and adjacent to the Action Area throughout the year if habitat conditions warrant. The longfin smelt DPS relative abundance is low and the species was recently listed by the Service as endangered.

Effects of the Action

Effects of the Action are all consequences to listed species or critical habitat that are caused by the proposed action, including the consequences of other activities that are caused by the proposed action. A consequence is caused by the proposed action if it will not occur but for the proposed action and it is reasonably certain to occur. Effects of the Action may occur later in time and may include consequences occurring outside the immediate area involved in the action.

Delta Smelt and its Critical Habitat

The proposed project is not expected to result in any additional effects not already analyzed in the Programmatic Biological Opinion. The proposed repairs will have an adverse effect on delta smelt if individuals are present in the open waters of the Carquinez Strait and are temporarily deterred from utilizing the aquatic environment due to physical (increased turbidity and suspended sediments) and noise/vibration disturbances from pile driving that interfere with normal behaviors. Avoidance of the Action Area by the delta smelt or deterrence from traversing through the channel during construction could also expose the delta smelt to predation that would not have occurred otherwise. Critical habitat impacts would be temporary changes to water quality and limited to the area around the piers. The construction effects to delta smelt and critical habitat are reduced by conducting the proposed project during the Service's recommended work-window which avoids the spawning and larval stages of the delta smelt's life cycle and incorporation of conservation measures consistent with the guidelines of the Programmatic Biological Opinion.

Longfin Smelt

Hydroacoustics

Longfin smelt may be affected by construction noise. Underwater sound pressure waves can harass and harm fish species (Hastings and Popper 2005; California Department of Transportation 2001). As the pressure wave passes through a fish, the swim bladder is rapidly squeezed due to the high pressure, and then rapidly expanded as the under-pressure component of the wave passes through the fish. This can cause adverse effects including rupture of the swim bladder, rupture of capillaries, internal hemorrhage, neurological stress, and auditory damage. Extreme sound waves can cause instantaneous death, latent death within minutes after exposure, or can occur several days later.

Elevated noise levels can cause sub-lethal injuries affecting survival and fitness. Similarly, if injury does not occur, noise may modify fish behavior that may make them more susceptible to predation. Fish suffering damage to hearing organs may suffer equilibrium problems and may have a reduced ability to detect predators and prey. Other types of sub-lethal injuries can place the fish at increased risk of predation and disease. Adverse effects on survival and fitness can occur even in the absence of overt injury. Exposure to elevated noise levels can cause a temporary shift in hearing sensitivity (referred to as a temporary threshold shift or TTS), decreasing sensory capability for periods lasting from hours to days (Hastings and Popper 2005; Popper and Hastings 2009; Hastings *et al.* 1996).

Turbidity and Contaminants

Construction activities would result in disturbances that are likely to temporarily increase turbidity and suspended sediment within the Action Area. Although longfin smelt are adapted to living in turbid environments, localized increases could adversely affect individual longfin smelt that may be present. Effects of increased turbidity and suspended sediment may temporarily degrade water quality, reduce prey resources, disturb habitat, and impede movements of longfin smelt. Spills or other chemical contamination from construction equipment could also negatively affect habitat and re-suspended sediments can sometimes elevate toxic levels in water. Implementation of the *Conservation Measures* would minimize but not eliminate the potential for these adverse effects to occur.

Habitat

The proposed project will result in the temporary loss of habitat within the Action Area due to increased activity, noise/vibration, and turbidity/suspended sediment. However, there will not be any permanent loss of habitat from the proposed activities.

Cumulative Effects

Cumulative Effects include the effects of future State, Tribal, local or private actions that are reasonably certain to occur in the Action Area considered in this biological opinion. Future Federal actions unrelated to the proposed project are not considered in this section, because they require separate consultation pursuant to section 7 of the Act. During this consultation, the Service did not identify any future non-Federal actions that are reasonably certain to occur in the

Action Area of the proposed project.

Conclusion

The Amorco Marine Terminal Repairs Project, as described, fits within the parameters of the level of effects analyzed in the Programmatic Biological Opinion and is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of the species or destroy or adversely modify its critical habitat.

After reviewing the current *Status of the Species* of the longfin smelt, the *Environmental Baseline* for the Action Area, the *Effects of the Action* and the *Cumulative Effects*, it is the Service's conference opinion that the Amorco Marine Terminal Repairs Project, as proposed, is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of the proposed longfin smelt DPS. This conclusion is based primarily on: (1) successful implementation of the *Conservation Measures* described in this biological opinion will minimize the adverse effects on individual longfin smelt, and (2) the project will only result in temporary effects to habitat for the longfin smelt DPS.

INCIDENTAL TAKE STATEMENT

Section 9 of the Act and Federal regulation pursuant to section 4(d) of the Act prohibit the take of endangered and threatened species, respectively, without special exemption. Take is defined as to harass, harm, pursue, hunt, shoot, wound, kill, trap, capture or collect, or to attempt to engage in any such conduct. Harm in the definition of "take" in the Act means an act which actually kills or injures wildlife. Such [an] act may include significant habitat modification or degradation where it actually kills or injures wildlife by significantly impairing essential behavioral patterns, including breeding, feeding, or sheltering (50 CFR 17.3) Under the terms of section 7(b)(4) and section 7(o)(2), taking that is incidental to and not the purpose of the agency action is not considered to be prohibited taking under the Act provided that such taking is in compliance with the proposed protective measures and the terms and conditions of an incidental take statement and occurs as a result of the action as proposed.

The measures described below are non-discretionary, and must be undertaken by the Corps so that they become binding conditions of any grant or permit issued to the applicant, as appropriate, for the exemption in section 7(o)(2) to apply. The Corps has a continuing duty to regulate the activity covered by this incidental take statement. If the Corps (1) fails to assume and implement the terms and conditions, or (2) fails to require the applicant to adhere to the terms and conditions of the incidental take statement through enforceable terms that are added to the permit or grant document, the protective coverage of section 7(o)(2) may lapse. In order to monitor the impact of incidental take, the Corps must report the progress of the action and its impact on the species to the Service as specified in the incidental take statement [50 CFR § 402.14(i)(3)(4)].

Amount or Extent of Take

The Service anticipates that juvenile and adult delta smelt and longfin smelt DPS will be subject to take in the form of harm from interference of normal behaviors within the Action Area;

therefore, the Service anticipates take in the form of harm of all delta smelt and longfin smelt DPS within the approximately ~~50-~~ 10,000-acre Action Area. However, due to the timing and duration of the proposed project, the Service anticipates take of individuals will be minimized. Upon implementation of the Reasonable and Prudent Measures, incidental take associated with the project will become exempt from the prohibitions described under section 9 of the Act.

Effect of the Take

In the accompanying biological opinion, the Service determined that the level of anticipated take is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of the delta smelt and longfin smelt DPS.

Reasonable and Prudent Measure

The Service has determined that the following Reasonable and Prudent Measure is necessary and appropriate to minimize the effects of the proposed project on the species:

1. Adverse effects to delta smelt and longfin smelt shall be minimized to the full extent possible.

Terms and Conditions

In order to be exempt from the prohibitions of section 9 of the Act, the Corps shall ensure compliance with the following term and condition, which implements the reasonable and prudent measure described above. This Term and Condition is non-discretionary.

1. The project proponent shall fully implement the proposed project, including the conservation measures, guidelines, implementing procedure, the Reasonable and Prudent Measure, and the corresponding Term and Condition as described in this biological opinion and the Programmatic Biological Opinion.

REINITIATION – CLOSING STATEMENT

This concludes reinitiation consultation on the Amorco Marine Terminal Repairs Project. As provided in 50 CFR § 402.16,

(a) Reinitiation of consultation is required and shall be requested by the Federal agency ~~or by the Service~~, where discretionary Federal involvement or control over the action has been retained or is authorized by law and:

- (1) If the amount or extent of taking specified in the incidental take statement is exceeded;
- (2) If new information reveals effects of the action that may affect listed species or critical habitat in a manner or to an extent not previously considered;
- (3) If the identified action is subsequently modified in a manner that causes an effect to the

listed species or critical habitat that was not considered in the biological opinion or written concurrence; or

(4) If a new species is listed or critical habitat designated that may be affected by the identified action.

(b) An agency shall not be required to reinitiate consultation after the approval of a land management plan prepared pursuant to 43 U.S.C. 1712 or 16 U.S.C. 1604 upon listing of a new species or designation of new critical habitat if the land management plan has been adopted by the agency as of the date of listing or designation, provided that any authorized actions that may affect the newly listed species or designated critical habitat will be addressed through a separate action-specific consultation. This exception to reinitiation of consultation shall not apply to those land management plans prepared pursuant to 16 U.S.C. 1604 if:

(1) Fifteen years have passed since the date the agency adopted the land management plan prepared pursuant to 16 U.S.C. 1604; and

(2) Five years have passed since the enactment of Public Law 115-141 [March 23, 2018] or the date of the listing of a species or the designation of critical habitat, whichever is later.

Please address any questions or concerns regarding this response Kim Squires, Section 7 Division Manager via email at Kim_Squires@fws.gov. Please refer to the Service File Number: 2023-0013317-S7-001-R001 in any future correspondence regarding this consultation.

Sincerely,

Jana Affonso
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